

ATTITUDE TO THE ARMED MOVEMENT AGAINST THE SOVIET AUTHORITY IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

Abdukamolova Mohlaroy Shukhratjonovna

Teacher of Fergana State University

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ABSTRACT

In view of the historical progress achieved today in independent Uzbekistan, the increasing interest of the population in the history of Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century justifies itself. This article provides information about the relationship to the armed movement against the Soviet power during the years of independence.

Turkestan Jadids planned to implement reforms step by step, to achieve progress and development only through peace, through the parliament. The course of events in 1917, as Abdurauf Fitrat, a great theoretician of the Jadidist movement, wrote at that time, "a new calamity in Russia - the Bolshevik calamity" completely changed the balance of power. Another devoted child of the Uzbek people, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, said "Rights are taken, not given!" slogan has become a rallying cry for the entire nation. The February revolution was important in awakening the Muslim population of Turkestan politically, and in the emergence of new forces that wanted to lead democratic changes to the political arena. Jadids became the core of the emerging national democratic forces. They connected their ideas about the development and independence of the indigenous peoples of the region with the ideas of the February Revolution and actively began to implement the principles they announced. Nicholas II abdicated on March 15 as a result of the coup d'état that took place in the center of the Russian Empire in February 1917.[1;366] The Provisional Government came to power. In this way, the rule of the empire in this country was put to an end. It was natural that this sudden political change would affect the life of dependent countries. In every city, uyezd, volost, and village across Turkestan, the old administrative offices were abolished by the Provisional Government, and executive committees of public organizations, i.e., committees called public security, began to be established in their place.[2; 18-19]. On December 13-15, 1916, a closed council was held in a narrow circle. Turkestans did not participate in this discussion. In the discussion, they pointed out that the decree on labor mobilization signed on June 25, 1916 was adopted in violation of the basic laws of the Russian Empire. . The following comments made by Deputy Jafarov about such violations of the law are particularly important as information showing the attitude of the authoritarian government towards Turkestan: "I would like to note that when it comes to Kyrgyz, Sart, Turkmen, the law is always ignored.

Everything is achieved by the power of authority, for this there is a large force consisting of administrators and mirshabs" [2; 11-12]

After coming to power in a coup in October 1917, Vladimir Lenin and the Bolsheviks struggled to maintain their rule against widespread popular opposition for the next few years. They overthrew the provisional democratic government and were inherently hostile to any form of popular participation in politics. In pursuit of the revolutionary goal, they used brutal methods to suppress real or perceived political enemies. [1;365]

After the Russian Empire came out of the war, the Jadids fought for a parliamentary monarchy, but after the events of February, they put forward a series of more comprehensive political demands. For example, expanding the rights of the local population, carrying out reforms in the management of the country, allocating seats in the State Duma based on the number of the country's population, ensuring the freedom of the national press. At the same time, a number of national-political parties and organizations, such as "Shorayi Islamiya" and "Ittifaq", were formed. At this time, the Jadids were able to follow the representatives of all levels of the social structure of the indigenous population. In Turkestan, the activities of the Jadids had an impact on the enlightenment of the local population, the strengthening of their national identity, and the rise of the struggle for freedom. Jadidism movement appeared in the country as the main spiritual force opposing the colonial policy of the imperial government. The small, elite group of Bolshevik revolutionaries who formed the core of the newly formed Communist Party dictatorship was ruled by decree, enforced by terror.

The tradition of strict centralization, where decision-making was concentrated at the highest party level, reached new dimensions under Joseph Stalin. As can be seen from many of these archival documents, little was included from below. The party elite determined the goals of the state and the ways to achieve them in almost complete isolation from the people. They believed that the interests of the individual should be sacrificed to the interests of the state promoting a sacred social mission. Stalin's "revolution from above" sought to build socialism through forced collectivization and industrialization, programs that caused enormous human suffering and loss of life.

Munavvargari Abdurashidkhanov headed the "Shorayi Islamiya" organization, which was founded in March 1917. In June 1917, "Shorayi Ulamo" and in July 1917 "Turk Adam Centralist Party" ("Turkistan Federalist Party") separated from it. These actions were one of the first attempts to consolidate the scattered national political forces, which considered protecting the interests of Turkestan as their goal. . On April 16-23, 1917, the first national congress of All-Turkistan Muslims was held in Tashkent on the initiative of "Shorayi Islamiya". About 150 delegates from all over Turkestan gathered there. The congress, which considered about 20 issues, made a decision to end colonialism in the country and return confiscated lands to the local population. In this meeting, it was also agreed to establish the Central Council of Muslims in Turkestan. This decision was later implemented in the form of the National Center. [2; 17-18]

The armed movement against the Soviet regime in Turkestan (1916-1943) is the struggle of the peoples of Central Asia against the Bolshevik rule and the invading Red Army (1918-1943). The armed actions against the Soviet regime in Turkestan are a special stage in

the history of the national liberation movement in Central Asia. The reason for the national liberation movement of the Turkic peoples was economic crises and anti-people laws.

According to its geographical scope, this movement is divided into 3 regions: Turkestan ASSR, Bukhara Republic and Khorezm Republic. Later, it continued in Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan SSR. According to the course of its development, the armed struggle passed through 2 periods: 1918-1924 and 1925-1935.

The 1st period of armed actions against the Soviet regime in Turkestan, the formation of the first armed groups is inextricably linked with the names of Kichik Ergash and Katta Ergash. Kichik Ergash, who led the army of the Turkestan Autonomous Government. On February 19-21, 1918, as a result of the war in the city of Koqan, he was defeated and retreated to the village of Bachqir in Koqan district. On February 26, Bachkir was attacked by 5 detachments of Red Guards and Armenian Dashnokdar.

After Kichik Ergash was killed in one of the battles on February 27, Katta Ergash began to fight against the Bolshevik colonial order in the Fergana Valley. Soon the movement spread to the entire Fergana Valley and Samarkand region.

The main reason for the armed actions against the Soviet regime in Turkestan was the colonialism and chauvinist policy of the Bolsheviks in the country. The first socialist measures carried out by the Bolsheviks (transfer of enterprises to the state, liquidation of private property, food distribution and grain monopoly, restriction of Islam and atheism, closing of mosques, madrasas, private schools and courts, confiscation of endowment lands, introduction of forced labor closing of markets, etc.) and the looting and raiding policy of the Red Army fighters gave the movement a special intensity and scope. These events led to the further expansion and development of the struggle.

The armed struggle is a movement that covers all groups and social strata of the population in terms of its driving forces (peasants, farmers, artisans, artisans and workers, representatives of very wealthy families - merchants, rich people and clerics) and organizational structure.

The national composition of the wrestlers consisted mainly of indigenous people - Uzbeks, Tajiks, Turkmens, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, Karakalpaks, and partly Uighurs. There were also some Bashkir and Tatar soldiers sent by the Russians and Validi, and a small number of officers from Turkey and Afghanistan. Between Madaminbek's troops and the Christian army of K. Monstrov stationed in Jalalabad, a mutual agreement was concluded to fight together against the Soviet regime and the Red Army (February 9, 1919). The increase in raids and robberies by the Red soldiers intensified the movement against them, and soldiers (young men) regularly joined the ranks of the fighters and new groups were formed.

With Walidy's arrival in Turkestan and entering the battlefield, the establishment of the "Turkistan National Unity" organization (February 8, 1921), the fighting escalated throughout the region. Other secret national organizations ("National Union", "National Independence") were also formed and actively supported the movement.

Scholars who had a leading position in Turkestan society at that time also served to a certain extent in preparing the ideology of the movement. However, due to the actions of some bigoted priests, the movement in many cases absorbed only the ideas of Islam and was limited to that.[3;380]

In the middle of 1918, about 100 kurbachis led the combat detachments against the units of the Red Army in the Fergana Valley. But it was falsified in the official documents of the Soviet government, actually on a national scale

- the movement and its members that the freedom movement wrongly called him "oppressor" K. Otaboev said "Printers".[2;29]

The armed struggle against the Bolsheviks and the forces of the Red Army in the Khorezm oasis began in the middle of 1918. Aggressive forces began to turn Petro-Aleksandrovsk (now Tortkol) into a base of attack against Khiva Khanate. Military forces were brought from Chorjoi through Amudarya. The territory of the right bank of Khorezm was occupied by Tsarist Russia in the 1970s and turned into a military fortress. The looting, violence, and bloodshed of the Red Army during their aggressive invasion of Khorezm and Bukhara countries were the main reasons that caused mass protests. These conflicts continued in later periods as well.

Aggressive. The Bolsheviks, who ordered and commanded the troops, stationed garrisons of red soldiers in the territories of the republics and relied on them, the military seized people's wealth and property, repressed people, carried out revolutionary changes, and led the trampling of national values. they did. This led to the expansion of the movement against the Red Army and its mass character. Almost all strata of the land population, primarily peasants, took part in the movement. This situation indicates that the leaders of the movement and those who joined them belong to different classes, and how wide, sharp, and intense the scope of protests, anger, and those who are ready for uncompromising battles are.

Armed struggle against aggressors in the Republic of Bukhara. The groups that fought against the Red Army, the uprisings that broke out in cities and districts began in all parts of the Republic of Bukhara - western, central, and eastern - and took a massive form. On the last day of August 1920, Amir Alim Khan, who left the capital Bukhara, came to Eastern Bukhara, gathered large forces, their number increased to 12,000, and later to 25,000, and battles were fought against the Red Army.

Ibrahimbek (1889-1932), Davlatmandbek and others led the struggle. In response to serious attacks, the command of the Red Army delivered new parts and a lot of weapons and put them into operation.[4;360]

At the beginning of 1921, the defeated Amir Alim Khan went to Afghanistan. In October of this year, the former military minister of Turkey Anwar Pasha (1881-1922) arrived in Bukhara, and after some time left for the eastern part of the country and joined the anti-Soviet forces. With the actions of Anwar Pasha, a united army was created in Eastern Bukhara and the western style of command was introduced. Anwar Pasha was martyred in one of the battles in the summer of 1922 on the hills of Baljuvan.

The struggle became intense in the central and western regions of the country. In the fall of 1920, armed groups were formed in Boysun, Denov, Sherabad, and Sariosia and started fighting. In December, uprisings began in Karshi, Shahrisabz, Yakkabog, Kitab, and Chiroqchi, the new authorities and red soldiers' garrisons suffered serious losses. Additional Red Army units were sent to these places as well.[4:355]

For a short period of time, an army under the leadership of Mulla Abdul Qahhar (1884-1924) was gathered in the districts of the capital Bukhara and military operations were

conducted. Also, dozens of groups in Bukhara, Karmana and Nurota operated under the leadership of Mulla Abdul Qahhar. Their large army marched to the capital Bukhara in early March 1922. After two days of intense fighting with the Red soldiers, they captured a large part of the city of Bukhara and held it in their hands for several hours. Then they occupied Bahauddin Naqshband shrine in the outskirts of the city. But in the battle with a large number of red soldiers (including Budyonny's cavalry) who arrived immediately, they were forced to retreat with heavy casualties from Bukharai Sharif and the shrine of Bahauddin.

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